

A Study to Assess the Effectiveness of Structured Teaching Programme (Stp) On Knowledge Regarding Central Line Associated Blood Stream Infection (Clabsi) Bundle Care Among Staff Nurses at Selected Hospital Bangaluru.

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Abstract: A pre experimental study has been conducted by using one group pre- test and post- test design using non-probability purposive sampling technique with the sample size of 60 staff nurse used for the study. The knowledge of staff nurse was assessed using structure teaching questionnaire followed by structure teaching program on central line associated blood stream infection (CLABSI) bundle care. Post test assessment was performed on the eighth day using the same tool. The results were described by using descriptive and inferential statistic. The study identified that the mean level of knowledge among staff nurse before administering structure teaching programme was 18.10 with the standard deviation 5.18 and the mean post test knowledge score was 24.01 with standard deviation of 3.27 showing high significance level with calculate p value <0.05. The study clearly showed that the structure teaching program was significantly effective in improving the knowledge of staff nurse regarding central line blood stream infection (CLABSI) bundle care.

Keywords: Effectiveness, Structure Teaching Programme, Central Line Associated Blood Stream Infection, Bundle Care.

INTRODUCTION

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), at any given time over 1.4 million people across the globe suffer from hospital-acquired infection (HAI). HAIs account for 2 million cases and about 80,000 deaths a year. WHO states that "Preventable Hospital infections are a major cause of death and disability for the patients.

The Centre of Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) estimate that the hospital acquired infection account for an estimate 1.7 million infection and 99,000 associated deaths each worldwide. In 2017-2020 an estimated 30,100 CLABSI still accrued in intensive care unit and wards of US acute care facilities each year.

The International Nosocomial Infection Control Consortium (INICC) study was conducted from January 2017 to December 2020 in 503 ICUs of Latin America, Asia, Africa, and Europe. Using the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention's (CDC) U.S. National Healthcare Safety Network (NHSN) defines for device-associated health care-associated infections, the authors collected data from 6,05,310 patients hospitalized in ICUs during 3,338,396 days. It is stated that the pooled rate of CLABSI in the INICC's ICUs, 4.9 per 1000 central line days, is nearly 5-fold higher than the rate reported from comparable US ICUs included in their last report.⁷

According to Hospital Infection Society of India, the rate of Central-line-associated blood stream infection, CLABSI (13.50%) was the most common health-care-associated infection followed by UTI (10.75%) and Ventilator Associated Pneumonia, VAP (6.15%). The mortality rate for device associated infections was (48.7%).⁸

These data and evidences supported that CLABSI bundle care is an important care area where every nurse who is working in hospital, especially in intensive or critical care units has to well verse with understanding of CLABSI bundle care. Hence, researcher thought to investigate the existing level of knowledge of nurses regarding CLABSI bundle care which will be followed by an educational intervention known as structured teaching programme to see the impact of structured teaching programme on knowledge level of nurses regarding CLABSI bundle care.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

"A study to Assess the Effectiveness of Structured Teaching Programme (STP) on Knowledge Regarding Central line associated blood stream infection (CLABSI) bundle care among the staff nurses at selected hospital Bengaluru"

OBJECTIVES

1. To assess the pre-test level of knowledge regarding CLABSI bundle care among staff nurses.
2. To evaluate the effectiveness of STP on knowledge regarding CLABSI bundle care among staff nurses.
3. To find out the association of pre-test knowledge score with their selected socio demographic variables.

HYPOTHESIS

The hypotheses will be tested at 0.05 level of significance

H₁: There will be significant difference between the pre test and post test knowledge score on CLABSI bundle care among staff nurse.

H₂: There will be significant association between pre-test knowledge score among staff nurses regarding CLABSI bundle care with their selected socio demographic variables.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:-

Based on the purpose or the objectives as well as the hypothesis framed for the study the research design selected for this study is Pre experimental one group pre-test post-test design in which pre-test is conducted followed by Structured teaching programme and then conducting post-test for the same group on 8th day. This design was selected because it seemed most appropriate to ascertain the knowledge of staff nurses on Central Line Blood Stream Infection (CLABSI) Bundle Care in Dr. B. R. Ambedkar Medical College and Hospital, Bengaluru.

Table 1
Frequency & Percentage Distribution of Respondents according to socio demographic variables
N=60

SI No	Demographic variables	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
1	Age (in yrs)		
	a) 20-30	24	40
	b) 31-40	17	28.3
	c) 41-50	13	21.7
	d) >5	6	10
2.	Gender		
	a) Male	28	46.7
	b) Female	32	53.3
3	Religion		
	a) Hindu	33	55
	b) Christian	20	33.4
	c) Muslim	5	8.3
	d) Others	2	3.3
4.	Marital status		
	a) Single	39	65
	b) Married	14	23.3
	c) Widower/Widow	5	8.4
	d) Divorced/Separated	2	3.3
5.	Type of family		
	a) Nuclear	34	56.7
	b) Joint	18	30
	c) Living alone	8	13.3
6.	Monthly income		
	a. Less than 15000	13	21.7
	b. Rs 15000 -20000	10	16.6
	c. Rs 20001 -25000	21	35
	d. Rs 25001 and above	16	26.7
7.	Educational Qualification		
	a. ANM	2	3.3
	b. GNM	26	43.3
	c. B.Sc (N)	16	26.7
	d. POST B.Sc (N)	16	26.7
8	Experience in years		
	a. <1year	17	28.3
	b. 1– 5 years	23	38.3
	c. 6 – 10 years	13	21.7
	d. >10 years	7	11.7
9.	Area of working		
	a. I.C.U	16	26.7
	b. Wards	26	43.3
	c. Health centre	5	8.3
	d. O.P.D.	13	21.7
10.	Source of information		
	a. Social media	10	16.7
	b. Friends	27	45
	c. In-service education	16	26.7
	d. Higher education	7	11.7

Table 2
Mean, median, mode, standard deviation and range of pre test knowledge scores of Respondents regarding CLABSI bundle care

Area of Knowledge	Number of Items	Mean	Median	Mode	Standard deviation	Range
Pre test scores	40	18.10	17	17	5.18	11-30
Post test scores	40	24.01	23	21	3.27	19-30

N = 60

Table 3
Frequency and Percentage distribution of respondents according to level of Knowledge regarding CLABSI bundle care

Level of Knowledge					
Pre test			Post test		
Inadequate f (%)	Moderate f (%)	Adequate f (%)	Inadequate f (%)	Moderate f (%)	Adequate f (%)
11 (18.3%)	38 (63.3%)	11 (18.3%)	00	42 (70%)	18 (30%)

n=60

Table 4
Mean, standard deviation and 't' value of pre-test and post-test knowledge scores regarding CLABSI bundle care

Aspects	Mean	Sd	Paired t Test
Pre-test	18.10	5.18	7.89*
Post-test	24.01	3.27	

N =60

Table 5
Chi-square values between levels of knowledge of respondents regarding CLABSI bundle care and their selected demographic variables.

N = 60

Sl No	Demographic variables	Knowledge score			d(f)	Chi square value	Level of significance
		Inadequate	Moderate	Adequate			
1	Age (in yrs)				6	5.84	NS
	a) 20-30	2	19	3			
	b) 31-40	4	10	3			
	c) 41-50	3	7	3			
	d) >50	2	2	2			
2	Gender				2	0.86	NS
	a) Male	6	16	6			
	b) Female	5	22	5			
3	Religion				6	2.15	NS
	a) Hindu	5	21	3			
	b) Christian	5	12	1			
	c) Muslim	1	3	9			
	d) Others	0	2				

4	Marital status						
	a) Single	7	25	7			
	b) Married	4	8	2	6	12.82	S
	c) Widower/Widow	0	5	0			
5	Type of family						
	a) Nuclear	7	19	8	4	3.46	NS
	b) Joint	3	14	1			
	c) Living alone	1	5	2			
6.	Monthly income			3			
	a. Less than 15000	1	9	2			
	b. Rs 15000 -20000	5	3	2	6	11.12	NS
	c. Rs 20001 -25000	4	15	4			
7.	Educational Qualification			0			
	a. ANM	0	2	3			
	b. GNM	4	19	5	6	4.74	NS
	c. B.Sc (N)	3	8	3			
8.	Experience in years			4			
	a. <1year	2	11	6			
	b. 1– 5 years	7	10	1	6	9.11	NS
	c. 6 – 10 years	1	11	0			
9.	Area of working			2			
	a. I.C.U	4	10	3			
	b. Wards	6	17	2	6	6.94	NS
	c. Health centre	1	2	4			
10.	Source of information			1			
	a. Social media	2	7	5			
	b. Friends	4	18	3	8	5.02	NS
	c. In-service education	5	8	2			
	Higher education						
	d. Higher education	0	5				

$\chi^2_{(2)} = 5.99$, $_{(6)} = 12.59$ ($p > 0.05$) NS – Not Significant

CONCLUSION

The findings revealed that nearly 18.3% of staff nurses had inadequate and adequate knowledge and 63.3% had moderate knowledge regarding Central Line Associated Blood Stream Infection Bundle Care. Whereas, the knowledge of staff nurses improved after STP and during the post- test 30% of staff nurses had adequate knowledge and 70% of the staff nurses had moderate knowledge. The STP Programme for staff nurses helped them to learn more about central line associated blood stream infection bundle care and apply their skills in clinical practice. There was significant impact between the post test knowledge scores with selected demographic variables such as Age, Marital status, Educational qualification and Experience. The study paved the path to enhance the knowledge of staff nurses on Central Line Associated Blood stream Infection Bundle Care.

Recommendations

- A similar study can be replicated on a large sample to generalize the findings.
- An experimental study can be undertaken with a control group of effective comparison of the result. In-service education on CLABSI bundle care should be made mandatory for all nurses.
- Training programme on bundle care should be conducted to all staff nurses to control and prevent CLABSI.
- Manuals, information booklets and self-instruction module, posters may be developed in areas of management and prevention.

- A study can be carried out to evaluate the efficiency of various teaching strategies like SIM, pamphlets, leaflets, computer assisted teachings

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